

ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY OF THORIUM. PART VIII. ALIPHATIC DICARBOXYLIC ACIDS

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In a study of the behaviour of aliphatic dicarboxylic acids, succinic acid is found to form a complex with thorium, and thus lead to loss of thorium. Further, at the p^n of optimum precipitation of thorium, the cerite earths also precipitate. Adipic acid is shown to precipitate quantitatively and free thorium after a double precipitation from the cerite earths in the p^n range 4.2 to 4.4. Thorium in monazite has been successfully estimated in this way.

James and Smith (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 34, 281) first employed sebacic acid for separating thorium from cerite earths. Metzger (*ibid.*, 1902, 24, 901) used fumaric acid in 40% ethanol with success for the same purpose. Gordon, Vanselow and Willard (*Anal. Chem.*, 1949, 21, 1323) observed that many dicarboxylic acids, while slow to react at ordinary temperatures, gave at high temperatures (70° - 85°) gelatinous precipitates with neutral thorium solutions. These latter investigators while advocating the use of tetrachlorophthalic acid, record experiments in which succinic acid at a p_n 3.3 precipitated only 80% of thorium; dibromosuccinic acid behaved more or less in the same way. Adipic acid was also reported along with other aromatic acids to have produced a gelatinous precipitate.

It is known that oxalic acid, the first member in the series, precipitates quantitatively thorium although it gives no separation from the rare earths, and sebacic acid, a higher homologue $(CH_2)_8(COOH)_2$, precipitates thorium completely and further gives good separation from the rare earths. One naturally expects a behaviour similar to that of sebacic acid with intermediates of higher molecular weight and an approach to that of oxalic acid in the case of lower homologues. This paper describes experiments conducted with succinic and adipic acids. While the latter behaves in a normal manner conforming to expectation, the other, succinic acid, presents a peculiar behaviour:

EXPERIMENTAL

The preparation of thorium and cerite earth solutions was described earlier (Venkataramanaih, Satyanarayanamurty and Raghava Rao, *this Journal*, 1950, 27, 81). Succinic acid, adipic acid and ammonium acetate were either Merck's guaranteed reagents or of B. D. H. AnalaR.

Succinic Acid

When neutral or slightly acid thorium nitrate and succinic acid solutions are brought together in the cold, there is no precipitation, but, on heating, there appears at about 50° a slight turbidity, a gelatinous precipitate between 70° and 80° which transforms itself into a finely divided crystalline substance on 15 to 20 minutes' boiling with constant mechanical stirring. The precipitation is not quantitative in agreement with the findings of Gordon *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). This depends upon two factors: (a) the p_n of

the solution and (b) the relative amount of the precipitant added. In the first instance a large excess of the precipitant is required, although, above a certain limit a slight dissolving action, presumably due to complex formation, may be noticed. Thus, when 0.0609 g. of ThO_2 was precipitated with 1, 2, 6 and 10 g. of succinic acid in a volume of 200 ml., 0.0507, 0.0523, 0.0535 and 0.0528 g. respectively of ThO_2 were weighed. The effect of p_H is indeed more marked and is indicated in the data below. The p_H was increased by the addition of suitable quantities of ammonium acetate, keeping the volume of the solution the same.

TABLE I

ThO_2 taken = 0.0609 g. Succinic acid added = 1 g.

p_H of the final liquid ...	2.7	3.2	3.9	4.5	4.9	5.1
ThO_2 added (g.) ...	0.0530	0.0587	0.0593	0.0597	0.0602	0.0593
Thorium pptd. (%) ...	87.0	96.4	97.4	98.0	98.9	97.4

Two important facts emerge out of these data. On the one hand, while increasing the p_H up to 4.9 favours precipitation of thorium, further increases lead to loss of thorium. This once again arises out of the solvent action of ammonium succinate formed in solution. This effect has been noticed in a more marked manner in precipitation directly with ammonium succinate. When 0.0609 g. of thorium was precipitated with 1 g. and 4 g. of ammonium succinate separately, the thorium precipitated amounted to 0.0604 g. and 0.0580 g. respectively, pointing to definite solvent action or complex formation.

Secondly, at the optimum p_H of 4.9 the precipitation of thorium is not complete, and even if it were, the reaction would be of no value in the separation of cerite earths since the latter precipitate appreciably at this p_H .

Adipic Acid

When a neutral solution (Congo-red indicator) of thorium nitrate is mixed with a solution of adipic acid in the cold, there results no precipitate; on adding a small amount of ammonium acetate most of the thorium is precipitated as a gelatinous mass proceeding to completion after heating for 15 minutes on a boiling water-bath. The precipitation of thorium by adipic acid proceeds best in the p_H range 4.2 to 4.4. The following procedure is recommended.

The thorium solution (containing about 0.1 g. ThO_2) is neutralised to Congo red and diluted to 100 ml. Adipic acid (1 g.) in 50 ml. of water is then added, followed by solid ammonium acetate (0.25 g.) The solution is heated on a boiling water-bath for 15 minutes. The resulting gelatinous precipitate is set aside to settle, filtered through Whatman No. 42 and washed with 0.5% solution of adipic acid. This is then ignited and weighed as ThO_2 .

Table II gives the results of some test estimations made in this way.

TABLE II

ThO ₂ taken (g.)	...	0.1218	0.0609	0.0305	0.0203	0.0061
ThO ₂ estimated (g.)	...	0.1220	0.0611	0.0304	0.0200*	0.0062*
Diff. (mg.)	...	+0.2	+0.2	-0.1	-0.3	+0.1

* The total volume was kept at half and the reagent added was also half the usual amount.

Separation from the Cerite Earths (Double Precipitation)

Thorium may be freed completely from the cerite earths by precipitating a second time. The first precipitate of thorium adipate is partially washed; it is then dissolved in 20 ml. of hot 1:1 nitric acid by pouring the liquid several times through the filter and catching the filtrate in the original beaker. The filtrate and washings are neutralised carefully to Congo red and the precipitation is repeated.

The thoria obtained on a single precipitation is largely contaminated with the ceria earths and this impurity increases with the amount of the ceria earths originally present. This is evident from the data in Table III A.

Results obtained after a double precipitation are shown in Table III B.

TABLE IIIA

Single precipitation.

Expt. No.	ThO ₂ present.	Cerite earths added.	ThO ₂ estimated.	Difference.
1	0.0609 g.	0.0995 g.	0.0628 g.	0.0019 g.
2	0.0609	0.0995	0.0631	0.0021
3	0.0609	0.4975	0.0705	0.0096

TABLE III B

Double precipitation.

ThO ₂ taken.	Cerite earths added.	ThO ₂ estimated.	Diff.	ThO ₂ taken	Cerite earths added.	ThO estimated	Diff.
0.0609 g.	0.0995 g.	0.0611 g.	+0.2 mg.	0.0609 g.	0.5970 g.	0.0612 g.	+0.3mg
0.0609	0.1590	0.0612	+0.3	0.0061	0.0597	0.0062	+0.1
0.0609	0.3920	0.0611	+0.2	0.0061	0.0935	0.0061	0.0
0.0609	0.4975	0.0611	+0.2				

Composition of the Precipitate

For this purpose the precipitate was finally washed with water and dried to a constant weight at 105°. On ignition to the oxide, different samples gave a slightly differing ratios of ThO₂: Th adipate. These values point to the formula

$O = \text{Th}(\text{OQC})_2(\text{CH}_3)_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ but it cannot be utilised in direct weighing of the precipitate.

Solubility of the Precipitate

It is known that ammonium acetate in addition to its useful buffer action, sometimes exercises a deleterious effect by forming a soluble complex with organic precipitates of metals. (Funk, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1942, 123, 241). Although the complete recovery of thorium suggests that this action, if it be present at all, should be of negligible magni-

tude, the following semi-quantitative experiments were performed to obtain more definite information. The thoroughly washed, moist thorium precipitate from the filter was shaken up for several hours with ammonium acetate solutions of varying concentrations both in the presence of adipic acid and without it. After settling, the clear supernatant liquid was pipetted out and analysed for thorium with the following results.

TABLE IV

Conc of Am. acetate soln.	Test for ThO_2 .	Approx. amount of ThO_2 present in 100 ml.	Remarks.
5%	Turbidity with oxalic acid.	10 mg.	Precipitate collected, washed and ignited to oxide.
1%	(1) Only opalescence with oxalic acid	3.5	Comparison with standard.
	(2) Colour with Alizarin-S	3.0	...
0.25%	Very faint colour with Alizarin-S	0.5	Colorimetric
5% Am. Ac. + 1 g. of adipic acid in 100 ml. of the soln.	Colour with Alizarin-S	1.0	Do
1% Am. Ac. + 1 g. of adipic acid in 100 ml. of the soln.	Very very faint colour with Alizarin-S	0.2	Do

It would thus appear that ammonium acetate in large excess forms complexes with thorium adipate but the amount thus formed is small and its already low solubility is further reduced by the presence of adipic acid. The loss of thorium on this count is none or insignificant.

Estimation of Thorium in Monazite

The method has been applied to the estimation of thorium in monazite. A sample of Travancore monazite was treated as described in Part I of this series (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 457) and the phosphate-free extract was precipitated with adipic acid. The results are shown in Table V. Results obtained with the classical *m*-nitrobenzoic acid procedure (Neish, *Chem. News*, 1904 90, 196) are also shown for comparison.

TABLE V

Monazite soln taken.	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid method.	Adipic acid method.	% ThO_2 in monazite.
	ThO_2 estimated.	ThO_2 estimated.	
10 ml.	0.1015 g.	0.1010 g.	8.08
10	0.1015	0.1014	8.11
20	0.2031	0.2026	8.10
20	0.2031	0.2028	8.11
		Mean	8.10